

8T – The Growth of Galaxies

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Abstract:

By analyzing the coupling constants series – author will make a prediction regarding the formation of galaxies, and in particular their growth. Since the coupling constants is infinite in kind, the size of the galaxies can not be evaluated as static, but rather varying overtime.

Introduction

The new 8T framework regard bosons as net curvature on the matric tensor, as presented in equation (1.34). The net curvature are of discrete amounts and is isomorphic to the prime numbers or one. Using three theorems made on a Lorentz manifold with (3,1)signature, it was possible to calculate the magnitude of the fine structure constant. Fermions are associated with arbitrary amounts of curvature in which curvature must vanish, their anti-commutation relation they appear in even amounts as in equation (1.35).

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1)$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1.1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \quad (1.2)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2} = 2N_1 + 1 \quad (1.3)$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2} = 2N_2 + 1 \quad (1.31)$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2} = 2N_3 + 1 \quad (1.32)$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.33)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta \gamma_i > 0 \quad (1.34)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.35)$$

According to this new framework of varying curvature, we can analyze the subject of growth of galaxies. The first point is that the growth of galaxies cannot be segmented in time, since there is an infinite amount of coupling constants, i.e. net curvatures on the metric tensor, causing fermions to cluster, the amount of fermions in the galaxy should be increasing over time. Now in consideration of the strength of each coupling term, the majority of matter should have been clustered in a relative short period as each coupling term is getting weaker and weaker. That is by the principle of least curvature, the ratio of net to total is aspiring zero in each term.

A second point is that all interactions are taking part of the formation of galaxies, not just a single interaction as gravity. In fact, gravity might be the least significant in the formation of galaxies according to its order in the series, and according to its weakness. Therefore, the first point was that the formation is a continuous process, the second point of this short essay, is that the amount of fermions being clustered is inversely proportional to the development of the coupling series. The more we develop the less matter being clustered. We can make the following predictions:

- (1) Galaxy matter density is inversely proportional to the distance from the core of the galaxy.
- (2) The amount of matter being clustered is inversely proportional to time.

We can try and put it in mathematical rigor, suppose we took the amount of elements which vanished into matter by equation (1.35) and parametrized it:

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i \rightarrow K$$

In addition, we can analyze the coupling term as a continuous analytical function over time ignoring the discrete amounts of curvature. Such is a valid representation due to equivalence of time arrows:

$$F_r \# \rightarrow (M, g, t)$$

$$\frac{\partial F_r}{\partial t} \propto^{-1} \frac{\partial K}{\partial t} \quad (1.36)$$

The term (1.36) is meant to express prediction (2), the more we develop F_r , the less matter being clustered to the galaxy formation. Galaxies mass distribution should get denser and denser from the core, and vice versa. This is vivid by the principle of least variation:

$$R = \frac{N_V}{T_V} \quad (1.37)$$

$$0.111 > 0.1 > 0.039 > 0.008 \dots \rightarrow 0 \quad (1.38)$$

As one is not a cosmologist, the ideas in this paper are mere predictions. Those are based solely on two equations and the idea of varying curvature. as to this moment it does not seem as if we can actually predict how much matter was clustered just as we can not discretize each coupling terms. In other words, we can not classify the coupling terms into discrete groups such as – the strong interactions are the those who are $N_V \leq Z$ and so on.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)
- [2] O. Manor. "The Principle of Least Curvature on Lorentz Manifold" In: (2021)
- [3] O. Manor. "The Coupling Constants Series and Rapid Galaxies Formation" In: (2021)